

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY

Department of Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning

**PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 21st
APRIL, 2021 at 2.00 pm.**

Members Present:

1. Dr. Naveen Kumar J.R. (HOD & Chairman BOS)
2. Prof. Anantharama H. (Member)
3. Prof. Om Prakash V. Bhat (Member)
4. Prof. Krishna Kaushik P. (Member)

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

- Amendment of changes in the syllabus for 2021 Scheme
- Preparation of Board of Examiners list
- Any other specific matter related to the Department activities

Agenda No.1

The Chairman of BOS proposed that in order to enrich the Knowledge and Skills of the students, and to implement the NEP 2020 for the 2021 batch, and set the syllabus accordingly as per the latest industry requirements and orientation towards the skill and employability. It is decided to consider the stakeholders feedback during setting of syllabus. to enhance the level of Knowledge & Skills of B.Tech Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning Engineering students. Furthermore, inclusion of value added courses (Employability Skill Enhancement Program, two technical internships and a social internship) and soft skill training was proposed. Hence, it was proposed in the meeting that the syllabus of Scheme 2021 will be forwarded to the Registrar (Academics) for the necessary approval.

Agenda No.2

The Chairman of BOS resolved to approve the Members of BOE and Panel of Examiners for the B. Tech Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning Examination for approval from the Registrar (Evaluation).

As there was no other issue to be discussed, the meeting was concluded at 4:00 pm.

Dr. Naveen Kumar J.R.
Chairperson, BoS